

Histopathological Spectrum of Renal Neoplasms in Nephrectomy Specimens in a Tertiary Care Hospital: A Retrospective Study

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Abstract:

Introduction: The kidney is a structurally complex organ that has evolved to carry out several important functions. Nephrectomy remains the standard of care for patients with a suspected renal mass. Renal neoplasms comprise a wide spectrum of neoplastic lesions with patterns distinct for children and adults. The present study was undertaken to estimate the histopathological spectrum of renal neoplasms in nephrectomy specimens and to correlate clinical presentation and demography with the different types of renal neoplasms.

Material and Methods: A retrospective record-based descriptive study was conducted in the Department of Pathology, Travancore Medical College, Kollam from nephrectomy specimens received in the department over five years (January 2019 to December 2023). The study included 70 nephrectomy specimens. WHO classification of tumours of kidney was used as reference to study the various histopathological patterns. WHO/International Society of Urological Pathology (ISUP) Grading system was followed for grading the renal neoplasms. Staging of renal neoplasms was done based on pathologic staging classification (pTNM) of American Joint Committee on Cancer (AJCC). The histologic patterns, clinical presentation, and demographic features were expressed in frequency and percentage.

Results: Out of 70 nephrectomy specimens, 49 (70%) were radical nephrectomy specimens and 21 (30%) were partial nephrectomy specimens. 62 were malignant, 6 were benign neoplasms and 2 were of low malignant potential. The majority of the tumours were detected incidentally (38.6%). Among symptomatic cases, the most common presenting symptom was hematuria (35.7%) followed by flank pain (21.4%). 52 (74.3%) out of the 70 specimens were from males. The most common age group was above 60 years (30 specimens, 42.9%). The left kidney (40 specimens, 57.1%) was more commonly affected. The interpolar region (27 specimens, 38.6%) was the most frequently involved site. Clear cell renal cell carcinoma (48 specimens, 68.6%) was the most common malignant renal neoplasm encountered followed by clear cell renal cell carcinoma with sarcomatoid differentiation (3 specimens, 4.3%), papillary renal cell carcinoma (3 specimens, 4.3%), chromophobe renal cell carcinoma (3 specimens, 4.3%), urothelial carcinoma of renal pelvis (3 specimens, 4.3%) urothelial carcinoma of renal pelvis with sarcomatoid differentiation (1 specimen, 1.4%) and collecting duct carcinoma (1 specimen, 1.4%). Multilocular cystic renal neoplasm of low malignant potential (1 specimen, 1.4%) and thyroid-like follicular renal cell carcinoma (1 specimen, 1.4%) falling under the category of low malignant potential were also identified. Both oncocytoma (3 specimens, 4.3%) and angiomyolipoma (3 specimens, 4.3%) were the most common benign tumours. Among the 61 malignant neoplasms which were graded, the commonest grade identified was Grade 2 (42 specimens, 68.9%) followed by Grade 1 (10 specimens, 16.4%). Based on the pathologic staging classification (pTNM) of American Joint Committee on Cancer (AJCC), out of the 64 malignant neoplasms, 37 specimens (57.8%) of tumours in the present study were of stage pT1 followed by pT3 accounting for 22 specimens (34.4%) and pT2 accounting for 5 specimens (7.8%)

Conclusion: The wide spectrum of renal neoplasms makes it essential to do a detailed histopathological examination to subtype, grade and stage the neoplasms as these help plan further management. The correct diagnosis has clinical implications leading to better prognostication, helping management decisions including targeted therapies, and identifying hereditary or syndromic associations which may necessitate appropriate genetic testing.

Keywords: Nephrectomy, Renal neoplasms, Histopathology, Clear cell renal cell carcinoma.

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Introduction

The kidney is a structurally complex organ that has evolved to carry out a number of important functions like excretion of waste products of metabolism, regulation of body water and salt, maintenance of blood pressure, and secretion of a variety of hormones and prostaglandins[1]. Nephrectomy is a common surgical procedure done for a variety of neoplastic and non-neoplastic diseases. It can either be simple in which the kidney is removed and is mainly done for non-neoplastic conditions or radical nephrectomy which is usually performed for renal neoplasms and involves the removal of the Gerota's fascia and its entire contents including the kidney, perinephric fat, and ipsilateral adrenal gland[2]. Nephrectomy remains the standard of care for patients with a suspected renal mass. Renal cell carcinoma is the 14th most common cancer in both sexes with increased number of cases being reported in Asia followed by Europe and ranks 16th in place for mortality[3]. Renal neoplasms comprise a wide spectrum of neoplastic lesions with patterns distinct for children and adults. Renal cell carcinoma may present with the classical clinical triad of hematuria, flank pain, and abdominal mass. Other manifestations include weight loss, anaemia, fever, and symptoms caused by a metastatic deposit. Some of the renal neoplasms may present with systemic paraneoplastic manifestations that include polycythemia, hypercalcemia, polyneuropathy, leukemoid reaction, systemic amyloidosis, gastrointestinal disturbances, hepatosplenomegaly and hepatic dysfunction[4,5,6]

Despite the newer techniques in imaging like CT scan or MRI, the histopathological examination of nephrectomy specimen remains the mainstay in the diagnosis, histological subtyping, and staging. There is limited recent data regarding the spectrum of renal neoplasms in Kerala. The present study was undertaken to investigate the frequency of various neoplastic lesions in nephrectomy specimens and to analyze the demographic and histopathological features of these lesions.

Materials and Method

Study Design: This retrospective record-based descriptive study was conducted in the Department of Pathology, Travancore Medical College, Kollam from nephrectomy specimens received in the department over five years (January 2019 to December 2023). Clearance from the Institutional Review Board and Ethics Committee (IEC No-220/24) was obtained.

Inclusion Criteria: All nephrectomy specimens (Radical/partial) with both benign and malignant neoplasms were included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

All nephrectomy specimens with cystic renal diseases, obstructive nephropathy, end-stage renal disease, renal inflammatory/infectious diseases, and traumatic rupture were excluded from the study. Autolysed specimens were also excluded.

A retrospective study of renal neoplasms in nephrectomy specimens was conducted in the Pathology department. The histopathological registers from 2019 January to December 2023 (five years) maintained in the Pathology department were retrieved. Demographic data including age and sex, presenting symptoms, radiological findings, gross specimen findings and microscopic findings including the histopathological patterns, nuclear grade, and stage were reviewed and recorded in the proforma. Based on these histopathological patterns, tumours were classified into benign and malignant renal neoplasms. WHO classification of tumours of the kidney was used as reference to study various histopathological patterns[2]. WHO/International Society of Urological Pathology (ISUP) Grading system was followed for grading renal neoplasms[2,4,7]. Staging of renal neoplasms was done based on pathologic staging classification (pTNM) of American Joint Committee on Cancer (AJCC)[8].

Statistical Analysis: The data was entered in Microsoft excel worksheet and the frequencies and percentages were calculated.

Results

70 nephrectomy specimens were received in our department during the five-year study period. Out of the 70 specimens received, 49 (70%) were radical nephrectomy specimens and 21 (30%) were partial nephrectomy specimens. 62 (88.6%) were malignant, 6 (8.6%) were benign and 2 (2.9%) were of low malignant potential. The majority of the tumours were detected incidentally (38.6%). Among symptomatic cases, the most common presenting feature was hematuria (35.7%). Other clinical symptoms included flank pain (21.4%), weight loss (2.9%), and burning micturition (1.4%) [Figure 1]. 52 (74.3%) out of the 70 specimens were from males and 18 (25.7%) were from females. The most common age group was above 60 years (30 specimens, 42.9%) followed by 40-60 year age group (28 specimens, 40%) and 20-40 year age group (12 specimens, 17.1%). The oldest patient was 82 years of age and the youngest patient was 26 years old.

The left kidney (40 specimens, 57.1%) was more commonly affected followed by right kidney (30 specimens, 42.9%). The interpolar region (27 specimens, 38.6%) was the most frequently

involved site followed by upper pole (23 specimens, 32.9%) and lower pole (20 specimens, 28.6%). The largest malignant tumour received following radical nephrectomy measured 12x10x10cm and the smallest measured 1.7x1.6x1 cm. The largest malignant tumour received following partial nephrectomy measured 5.2x5x2.5 cm and the smallest measured 1.5x1.3x1 cm. The largest benign tumour received measured 13x12x5 cm and the smallest measured 4x2x3 cm.

In contrast-enhanced CT abdomen, renal cell carcinomas had varied appearances from solid relatively homogenous to markedly heterogenous enhancement with cystic or necrotic changes. Benign lesions like oncocytoma showed heterogenous contrast enhancement with few showing central stellate scar. Angiomyolipomas appeared as large mass with increased fat density and prominence of vessels in the lesion. The low malignant potential neoplasms like multilocular cystic renal neoplasm of low malignant potential and thyroid-like follicular renal cell carcinoma appeared as isodense to hypodense mass lesions.

Based on the WHO classification of tumours of the kidney, the most common histopathological type were of epithelial origin [Table 1]. Clear cell renal cell carcinoma was the most common malignant neoplasm (48 specimens, 68.6%), [Figure 2] followed by clear cell renal cell carcinoma with sarcomatoid differentiation (3 specimens, 4.3%), [Figure 3] papillary renal cell carcinoma (3 specimens, 4.3%), [Figure 4] chromophobe renal cell carcinoma (3 specimens, 4.3%), [Figure 5] urothelial carcinoma of renal pelvis (3 specimens, 4.3%), urothelial carcinoma of renal pelvis with

sarcomatoid differentiation (1 specimen, 1.4%) [Figure 6] and collecting duct carcinoma (1 specimen, 1.4%) [Figure 7]. Among the neoplasms, two fell into the category of low malignant potential that included multilocular cystic renal neoplasm of low malignant potential (1 specimen, 1.4%) [Figure 8] and thyroid-like follicular renal cell carcinoma (1 specimen, 1.4%) [Figure 9]. Among the benign epithelial tumours, oncocytoma was the most common (3 specimens, 4.3%) [Figure 10]. Among the benign mesenchymal tumours, angiomyolipoma was the most common (3 specimens, 4.3%) [Figure11].

A total of 61 specimens were graded after excluding the 6 benign neoplasms and 3 chromophobe renal cell carcinoma out of the total 70 specimens. As per the WHO/International Society of Urological Pathology (ISUP) Grading system, the commonest grade identified was Grade 2 (42 specimens, 68.9%) followed by Grade 1 (10 specimens, 16.4%), Grade 3 (5 specimens, 8.2%) and Grade 4 (4 specimens, 6.6%) [Fig 12]. A total of 64 specimens were staged after excluding 6 benign neoplasms out of 70 specimens. Based on the pathologic staging classification (pTNM) of American Joint Committee on Cancer (AJCC), 37 specimens (57.8%) of tumours in the present study were of stage pT1 followed by pT3 accounting for 22 specimens (34.4%) and pT2 accounting for 5 specimens (7.8%) [Fig 13]. Nodal metastasis was identified in two cases each of clear cell renal cell carcinoma and clear cell renal cell carcinoma with sarcomatoid differentiation and one case of urothelial carcinoma of renal pelvis. One case of collecting duct carcinoma presented with distant metastasis.

Figure 1: Clinical presentation

Table1: Frequency and histological types of renal neoplasms.

Histopathology	Frequency (n=70)	Percentage
Clear cell renal carcinoma	48	68.6
Clear cell renal carcinoma with sarcomatoid differentiation	3	4.3
Papillary renal cell carcinoma	3	4.3
Chromophobe renal cell carcinoma	3	4.3
Urothelial carcinoma of renal pelvis	3	4.3
Urothelial carcinoma of renal pelvis with sarcomatoid differentiation	1	1.4
Collecting duct carcinoma	1	1.4
Multilocular cystic renal neoplasm of low malignant potential	1	1.4
Thyroid-like follicular renal cell carcinoma	1	1.4
Oncocytoma	3	4.3
Angiomyolipoma	3	4.3

Figure 2: A). Radical nephrectomy gross specimen of a fairly circumscribed clear cell renal cell carcinoma with variegated appearance. B). Microscopy showing nests of clear cells intervened by vascular channels (H&E, 20X).

Figure 3: A).Radical nephrectomy gross specimen of clear cell renal cell carcinoma with sarcomatoid differentiation. B). Microscopy shows atypical spindle cells, tumour giant cells and marked nuclear pleomorphism (H&E, 40X).

Figure 4: A). Partial nephrectomy gross specimen of a well circumscribed papillary renal cell carcinoma. B). Microscopic image of papillary renal cell carcinoma showing papillary cores with foamy macrophages (H&E, 40X).

Figure 5: Microscopic image of chromophobe renal cell carcinoma showing nests of tumour cells with plant like cell border (H&E, 20X).

Figure 6: A). Radical nephrectomy gross specimen of Urothelial carcinoma of renal pelvis with sarcomatoid differentiation. B). Microscopy showing papillary nests with sarcomatoid differentiation (H&E, 20X).

Figure 7: Collecting duct carcinoma with tumour cells arranged in tubulocystic pattern (H&E, 20X).

Figure 8: A). Radical nephrectomy gross specimen of multilocular cystic renal neoplasm of low malignant potential showing cystic lesion with brown areas. B). Microscopic image of multilocular cystic renal neoplasm of low malignant potential showing cyst lined by clear cells (H&E, 40X).

Figure 9: A). Radical nephrectomy gross specimen of well circumscribed thyroid-like follicular renal cell carcinoma. B). Microscopic image of thyroid-like follicular renal cell carcinoma showing cells arranged in micro and macrofollicles with inspissated colloid like material (H&E, 40X).

Figure 10: A). Partial nephrectomy gross specimen of a well circumscribed oncocytoma. B). Solid nests of eosinophilic oncocytic tumour cells in an oedematous stroma (H&E, 20X).

Figure 11: A). Radical nephrectomy gross specimen of angiomyolipoma showing fairly circumscribed mass with extensive fat admixed with areas of hemorrhage. B). Microscopy shows mixture of myoid spindle cells, adipose tissue and thick walled vessels (H&E, 20X).

Figure 12: WHO/ISUP grading of malignant renal neoplasms.

Figure 13: AJCC (pTNM) staging of malignant renal neoplasms.

Discussion

Renal neoplasms can be classified into benign and malignant renal cell tumours, metanephric tumours, mesenchymal tumours occurring mainly in children and adults, nephroblastic and cystic tumours occurring in children, mixed epithelial and stromal tumours, neuroendocrine tumours, miscellaneous tumours and metastatic tumours. Renal cell carcinoma (RCC) and Wilm's tumour are the common malignant renal neoplasm in adults and children respectively. Among the malignant renal neoplasms in adults, clear cell renal cell carcinoma is the most common. Oncocytoma and angiomyolipoma are the commonest among the benign epithelial and mesenchymal renal tumours in adults. Etiological factors that may lead to renal malignancies include obesity, smoking, hypertension, acquired cystic kidney disease, and occupational exposure (Trichloroethylene)[2,6]. WHO/International Society of Urological Pathology (ISUP) Grading system is the grading system being followed for grading renal neoplasms[2,4,7]. Staging of renal neoplasms is done based on the pathologic staging classification (pTNM) of American Joint Committee on Cancer (AJCC)[8]. The present study was undertaken to study the frequency of various neoplastic lesions in nephrectomy specimens and to analyze the demographic and histopathological features of these lesions.

A total of 70 nephrectomy cases were retrieved and reviewed for the present study. Among the nephrectomy specimens, radical nephrectomy procedure outnumbered partial nephrectomy in our study which was similar to the study done by Basnet et al.[9]. In the present study, the maximum

number of renal neoplasms were seen in individuals > 60 years of age (42.9%) followed by patients under the age group 40-60 years (40%) and 20-40 age group (17.1%). In comparison, in studies done by Basnet et al.,[9], Bajaj H et al.,[10], Vinay et al., [11] and Suryawanshi et al.,[12] the highest percentage of patients undergoing nephrectomy belonged to 40-50 years followed by 50-60 years of age. Males (74.3%) outnumbered females (25.7%) in the present study which was similar to studies done by Basnet et al.,[9], Bajaj H et al.,[10], Vinay et al.,[11], Suryawanshi et al.,[12], Thakur et al.,[13] and Kumari A et al.,[14]. Out of the 70 specimens, 62 specimens (88.6%) were malignant and 6 cases were benign (8.6%). This result was similar to studies done by Basnet et al.,[9], Suryawanshi et al.,[12], Gupta S et al.,[15], Kumar MR et al.,[16], Lal L et al.,[17] and Dr Suma et al.,[18] where the proportion of malignant neoplasms were significantly higher. In the present study, the highest proportion of the tumors were incidentally detected (38.6%) and among symptomatic cases, the most common presenting feature of renal neoplasms was hematuria (35.7%) followed by flank pain, (21.4%) weight loss (2.9%) and burning micturition (1.4%). In studies done by Bajaj H et al.,[10], Suryawanshi et al.,[12], and Kumari A et al.,[14], flank pain was the commonest symptom followed by burning micturition, hematuria, pyuria, fever, lump abdomen, vomiting and only a few were incidentally detected neoplasms. In the present study left kidney (57.1%) was seen to be more involved than the right kidney (42.9%) which was similar to studies done by Suryawanshi et al.,[12] and Shah et al.,[19]. In contrast, right kidney was more commonly affected accounting for around

54%-57% than the left kidney (42%-45%) in studies done by Basnet et al.,[9] and Thakur et al.,[13]. In the present study, interpolar region was the predominantly involved site (38.6%) followed by the upper pole (32.9%) and lower pole (28.6%). Studies done by Kumari A et al.,[14] and Shah et al.,[19] showed neoplasms most commonly involving the upper pole followed by the lower pole and then the interpolar region.

On analyzing the histopathological patterns, tumours of epithelial origin predominated among both malignant and benign neoplasms which were similar to studies done by Basnet et al.,[9], Suryawanshi et al.,[12], Gupta S et al.,[15], Kumar MR et al.,[16], Lal L et al.,[17] and Dr Suma et al.,[18]. Malignant renal neoplasms outnumbered benign and the commonest malignant neoplasm encountered was clear cell renal cell carcinoma (68.6%) followed by papillary renal cell carcinoma (4.3%) and chromophobe renal cell carcinoma (4.3%). This was similar to studies done by Basnet et al.,[9], Bajaj H et al.,[10], Suryawanshi et al.,[12], Gupta S et al.,[15], Kumar MR et al.,[16], Lal L et al.,[17] and Dr Suma et al.,[18]. Clear cell renal cell carcinoma with sarcomatoid differentiation and urothelial carcinoma of renal pelvis each accounted for 4.3%, while urothelial carcinoma of renal pelvis with sarcomatoid differentiation and collecting duct carcinoma accounted for 1.4% each in the present study. In addition, tumours of low malignant potential were also identified which included multilocular cystic renal neoplasm of low malignant potential and thyroid-like follicular renal cell carcinoma (1.4% each). In the study done by Bhat et al.,[20], one case of multilocular cystic renal neoplasm of low malignant potential was identified. Among the benign tumours, the most common were oncocytoma and angiomyolipoma which was similar to the studies done by Vinay et al.,[11] and Suryawanshi et al.,[12]. Angiomyolipoma was the most common among the benign tumours in studies done by Gupta S et al.,[15], Kumar MR et al.,[16] and Lal L et al.,[17].

As per the WHO/ISUP grading system, in the present study, among the 61 malignant tumors which were graded, nuclear Grade 2 was the most common presentation accounting for 68.9% followed by Grade 1 (16.4%), Grade 3 (8.2%) and the least common being Grade 4 (6.6%) which was similar to studies done by Shah et al.,[19] and Bhat et al.,[20]. Following pTNM AJCC classification, out of the 64 malignant tumours which were staged, the maximum number of specimens in the present study were within pT1 (57.8%) followed by pT3 (34.4%) and pT2 (7.8%). In studies conducted by Basnet et al.,[9], Shah et al.,[19] and Bhat et al.,[20] the maximum number of cases were within pT1 (71.4%) followed by pT2 (14.2%).

Even though this study throws light into the current profile of renal neoplasms, the limitation of the present study is that it is a single center study whose data may not be generalisable.

Conclusion

Nephrectomy remains the standard of care for patients with a suspected renal mass. The wide spectrum of renal neoplasms makes it essential to do a detailed histopathological examination to subtype, grade, and stage the neoplasms as these help plan further management. The correct diagnosis has clinical implications leading to better prognostication, helping management decisions including targeted therapies, and identifying hereditary or syndromic associations which may necessitate appropriate genetic testing.

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